

REPOPSI End-Project Evaluation Using the CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025

Source

CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2022). CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025 (V01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051012>

About the Repository

REPOPSI (www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/) is an open repository for psychological measures, scales, tests, and other research instruments in Serbian. It is maintained by researchers at the Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences ([LIRA](#)) at the University of Belgrade Faculty of Philosophy. REPOPSI instruments are deposited in an Open Science Framework (OSF) project at osf.io/5zb8p/.

Date of Evaluation

July 30, 2023

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This report was created as part of the project titled “TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs”, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017536. The project has received support from the [EOSC Future](#) through the [RDA Open Call mechanism](#), based on evaluations of external, independent experts.

Context and Evaluation Method

We used the CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Digital Repositories Requirements v01.00 2023-2025 to evaluate REPOPSI at the end of the project titled "TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs" (project team members: Aleksandra Lazić, Ljiljana Lazarević, Danka Purić, Iris Žeželj, Obrad Vučkovic).

We have previously used this test at the beginning of the project. The report of that preliminary self-assessment, from December 2022, is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7535052>.

For the end-project self-evaluation, we indicated the compliance level for each of the Requirements on a binary scale (0 – In Progress: the repository is in the implementation phase; 1 – Implemented: the requirement has been fully implemented by the repository). Additionally, we provided a detailed supporting narrative describing the response statements as well as evidence for each requirement.

R0. Background Information & Context

(1) Re3data Identifier.

Response

<https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100013441>

(2) Repository type.

Response

- Generalist repository
- **Specialist repository: Social Sciences - Psychology**

(3) Overview.

Response

REPOPSI (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/>) – Repository of Psychological Instruments in Serbian (srp. Repozitorijum psiholoških instrumenta na srpskom jeziku) is an open repository that enables users to freely access and share psychological instruments in Serbian and other languages. It was established in 2020 by the Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences ([LIRA](#)) at the University of Belgrade – Faculty of Philosophy and is hosted on the Open Science Framework (OSF) at <http://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/5ZB8P>.

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REPOPSI holds psychological measures, scales, tests, and other instruments commonly used in social and behavioral science research. While it is primarily intended for Serbian instruments (that is, instruments translated/adapted into Serbian or originally developed by local scientists), it also documents English and multilingual instruments.

REPOPSI is a growing collection – it currently contains 200 instrument records, half of which are available in both Serbian and English. A total 171 instruments are available in full in the Repository, while the rest are not deposited in the Repository and are available upon request from the contact author or elsewhere online.

Instruments found in REPOPSI may be used under the Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International ([CC BY-NC-SA 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/)) license. They can be freely accessed and used without permission for noncommercial purposes, provided instrument authors and translators are cited.

All of the instruments are stored as both PDF and ODT files; scoring and recoding code is also available for some of them (usually as an SPSS syntax file or R script).

REPOPSI metadata can be found: (a) in tabular [CSV](#) and [XLSX](#) files deposited on the OSF; (b) in a [Google spreadsheet](#) searchable using an [interactive web app](#); (c) in OSF metadata fields of the OSF component in which the instrument is stored; and (d) in XML documents, in compliance with the DataCite Metadata Schema, deposited into OSF components of every instrument. All metadata are in English.

(4) **Designated Community.**

Response

REPOPSI's target user community are researchers and students in psychology, but also in other social and behavioral sciences. Moreover, REPOPSI is used in teaching university courses in psychometrics and related fields. As currently half of instrument records are available in both Serbian and English, REPOPSI is useful to both local and international researchers (e.g. for multi-country research projects).

(5) **Levels of Curation.**

Response

- A. Content distributed as deposited
- B. Basic curation – e.g. brief checking, addition of basic metadata or documentation
- C. **Enhanced curation – e.g. conversion to new formats during ingest, enhancement of documentation and metadata**

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D. Data-level curation – as in C above, but with additional editing of deposited data

All deposits are subject to enhanced curation and some deposits are also subject to data-level curation. Enhanced curation involves converting submitted data to common preservation formats (PDF and ODT files), manual basic checks of metadata (e.g. whether the provided URLs for sources are functional), and putting metadata into machine-readable XML documents. Data-level curation involves manual checks of metadata accuracy and consistency and editing of documentation. For deposits with poor quality metadata this includes, for example, adding missing DOIs or missing instrument citations. Curation workflow is described in the REPOPSI Maintenance Manual and Workflow (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8195983>).

(6) Cooperation and outsourcing to third parties, partners and host organizations.

Response

The REPOPSI website (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/>) is hosted by the University of Belgrade Computer Centre (RCUB). RCUB is a publicly funded organizational unit of the University of Belgrade and the central infrastructure and computer service provider for the University's faculties and institutes. Since the Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences (LIRA) is part of the University of Belgrade – Faculty of Philosophy, it was assigned the *f.bg.ac.rs* domain. These hosting services are provided free-of-charge.

The psychological instruments available in full in REPOPSI are stored on the Open Science Framework (OSF; osf.io) (at <http://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/5ZB8P>), which is a free and open platform. While REPOPSI's data preservation, persistence, and integrity capabilities are largely dependent on the OSF, the OSF is not in any way responsible for REPOPSI contents or actions.

(7) Applicants renewing their CoreTrustSeal certification: summary of significant changes since last application.

Response

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Organizational Infrastructure

Mission & Scope (R01)

R01. The repository has an explicit mission to provide access to and preserve digital objects.

Self-Assessed Compliance Level:

1 – Implemented: the requirement has been fully implemented by the repository

Response

The mission statement and scope of REPOPSI are clearly stated on the website's homepage (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/>). This source also describes REPOPSI's endorsement of the FAIR Data Principles and the [TRUST Principles for Digital Repositories](#); the latter include the Sustainability principle, which refers to Repository's commitment to ensure that services are sustained and that data holdings are preserved for the long-term. REPOPSI's Terms of Use (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/terms-of-use/>) and Privacy Policy (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/privacy-policy/>) are transparently declared on the website.

Rights Management (R02)

R02. The repository maintains all applicable rights and monitors compliance.

Self-Assessed Compliance Level:

1 – Implemented: the requirement has been fully implemented by the repository

Response

Data access and use in REPOPSI are declared in the Repository Terms of Use (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/terms-of-use/>), on the REPOPSI website (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/how-to-search-repopsi/>, "Citation" section), and on the OSF Wiki page (<https://osf.io/5zb8p/wiki/home/>). REPOPSI data and metadata are available under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International ([CC BY-NC-SA 4.0](#)) license. It should be noted, however, that different access and reuse policies are in place for the three data availability types.

The psychological instruments available in full in the Repository (first availability type) are deposited on the OSF and are under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0

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International ([CC BY-NC-SA 4.0](#)) license. It is explained to users that those instruments can be freely accessed and used without permission for noncommercial purposes (e.g. academic research, clinical or educational purposes), provided instrument authors and translators are cited, and that any adapted material they produce should be distributed under the same license as the original. Machine-readable Creative Commons licenses for every deposited instrument are in XML files also deposited on the OSF.

For instruments that do not meet these copyright requirements only the metadata is available to users (via the tabular [CSV](#) and [XLSX](#) files deposited on the OSF and in a [Google spreadsheet](#) searchable using an [interactive web app](#)). These instruments are either marked as available “From Contact person” (second availability type) or “Elsewhere online” (third availability type).

Access and license information are mandatory fields in the REPOPSI contribution form (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/how-to-contribute-to-repopsi/>). When flagged by users, REPOPSI removes instruments from open access, if needed. Monitoring compliance at reuse is currently not possible.

Continuity of Service (R03)

R03. The Repository has a plan to ensure ongoing access to and preservation of its data and metadata.

Self-Assessed Compliance Level:

0 – In Progress: the repository is in the implementation phase

Response

REPOPSI’s plans and practices to ensure long-term data preservation and use are still in the conceptualization phase. While no funding is needed at this point, REPOPSI will have to sufficiently plan for risk mitigation, disaster recovery, and succession.

Legal & Ethical (R04)

R04. The repository ensures to the extent possible that data and metadata are created, curated, preserved, accessed and used in compliance with legal and ethical norms.

Self-Assessed Compliance Level:

1 – Implemented: the requirement has been fully implemented by the repository

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Response

The license for the instruments available in full in the Repository (i.e. Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International [CC BY-NC-SA 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/) license) was chosen so that REPOPSI use can be in line with the standards and norms of its target user community (i.e. academic researchers and students). Furthermore, most of the instruments that academic researchers and students develop, adapt or translate can be reused under this license. The REPOPSI contribution form (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/how-to-contribute-to-repopsi/>) clearly describes the difference between the instruments that can be opened in REPOPSI under this Creative Commons license and the instrument that cannot, which often include so-called commercial tests, which are standardized instruments that have been copyrighted and that are available through the test publisher or other commercial vendors. These instruments are usually available only if purchased and one often needs to have special qualifications to administer them. In the case of commercial tests, the depositor has the option to provide only the metadata so that the instrument is available to REPOPSI users either “From Contact person” or “Elsewhere online”. The same applies to the instruments for which it would be unethical to make them available open access (e.g. intelligence tests, human resource selection tests). While REPOPSI relies on the depositor to decide whether non-commercial tests can be made open access, the Repository admin can request more information from them to confirm that their decision was correct. When submitting the translations/adaptations of the instruments which they did not originally develop, the REPOPSI contribution form (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/how-to-contribute-to-repopsi/>) reminds the depositors to check the instrument terms of use with the original instrument authors. The (meta)data for some instruments include the email address(es) of the contact person(s) – these are the only type of sensitive data that REPOPSI holds. The depositors consent to making this information publicly available by submitting the REPOPSI contribution form.

Governance & Resources (R05)

R05. The repository has adequate funding and sufficient numbers of staff managed through a clear system of governance to effectively carry out the mission.

Self-Assessed Compliance Level:

0 – In Progress: the repository is in the implementation phase

Response

From March 2020 (when REPOPSI was launched) to October 2022, no funding was needed or used for Repository operations. In 2022, REPOPSI was awarded a €50,000 grant, after applying to an [Open Call](#) funded by [EOSC Future](#) and managed by Research Data Alliance (RDA), for a [project](#) that was active from October 27, 2022 to July 27, 2023. As explained in this blog post

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(<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/repopsi-project/>), the funding was used to improve technologies and services, promote the Repository, increase the number of records, and enhance metadata. A part of this funding will also go into sustaining REPOPSI services for the long term (e.g. paying for the hosting of the interactive search app). No funding is needed for the REPOPSI website hosting (since it is provided by RCUB) or for the OSF (since it is offered free-of-charge). While, at the moment, REPOPSI has adequate funding, it will have to develop the future sustainability plan including possible funding model scenarios and actions.

The REPOPSI website is hosted by RCUB, which is [an organizational unit of the University of Belgrade](#); in line with their mission and the role of a publicly funded institution, RCUB seeks to provide reliable and secure services. The psychological instruments for REPOPSI are deposited on the OSF platform. The OSF is the flagship product of the Center for Open Science (COS; <https://www.cos.io/>). COS is a non-profit organization with the mission of increasing the openness, integrity, and reproducibility of scientific research. COS established a preservation fund to host a static version of the OSF in the event that COS ceases to function. This fund is sufficient for 50+ years of read access hosting at present costs (<https://help.osf.io/article/546-getting-started-faq-s>).

The REPOPSI team currently consists of one administrator who manages the Repository, four mentors who supervise Repository decisions and actions, and three active student associates who help curate and deposit instruments. Their roles and responsibilities are described on the [“Our team” page](#) of the website, the “Maintenance crew members” section of the [REPOPSI Maintenance Manual and Workflow](#), and on the “REPOPSI team” section on the [OSF Wiki page](#). The REPOPSI team members are engaged on a volunteer basis and there is no official system of governance. REPOPSI currently does not have a budget for external engagement.

Expertise & Guidance (R06)

R06. The repository adopts mechanisms to secure ongoing expertise, guidance and feedback-either in-house, or external.

Self-Assessed Compliance Level:

0 – In Progress: the repository is in the implementation phase

Response

The REPOPSI team currently consists of four in-house psychology experts (introduced on the [“Our team” page](#) of the website), reflecting the scientific scope of the Repository. During the EOSC Future/RDA project that lasted from October 27, 2022 to July 27, 2023, REPOPSI was able to secure funding to adopt and maintain new technologies in order to remain valuable to its Designated Community as well as to recruit one external library expert. Currently, however, REPOPSI does not

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have a budget for future external engagement or future training and professional development of its staff. REPOPSI will need to secure access to external advisers, including legal, IT, data management, and data security experts.

Digital Object Management

Provenance and authenticity (R07)

R07. The repository guarantees the authenticity of the digital objects and provides provenance information.

Self-Assessed Compliance Level:

1 – Implemented: the requirement has been fully implemented by the repository

Response

The enhanced and data-level curation that REPOPSI provides contribute to guaranteeing the authenticity of the digital objects and enhancing their provenance information (by, for example, checking whether the URLs that the depositor provided for sources are functional or replacing them with DOIs, where possible; adding missing DOIs; adding missing instrument citations or authors and checking the accuracy of citation/author information).

Once a digital object is approved and published, only the REPOPSI team members are able to change the (meta)data. If necessary, users may contact REPOPSI to correct and add the metadata and deposit new versions of the instrument. For all (meta)data files deposited on the OSF, a built-in version control maintains a record of all previous copies of a file. Users can access the list of the file's version history, where they are able to copy two types of version IDs (MD5 and SHA-2) and download previous versions of a file

(<https://help.osf.io/article/282-file-revisions-and-version-control>).

While there is no formalized identification check in place, depositors have to leave their email address in the contribution form. When needed, the REPOPSI team communicates with them directly via email.

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Deposit & Appraisal (R08)

R08. The repository accepts data and metadata based on defined criteria to ensure relevance and understandability for users.

Self-Assessed Compliance Level:

1 – Implemented: the requirement has been fully implemented by the repository

Response

REPOPSI is intended for psychological measuring instruments, such as various scales, questionnaires and tests. While REPOPSI prioritizes Serbian instruments (i.e. instruments translated/adapted into Serbian or originally developed by local scientists), it also documents English and multilingual instruments. To be recorded (and deposited) in REPOPSI, the original instrument (i.e. the instrument in the language in which it was originally developed) has to be published in a scientific publication or expert report (including journal articles, conference proceedings, doctoral theses, preprints etc., but not including master's and graduate theses). These prerequisites are stated at the beginning of the REPOPSI contribution form (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/how-to-contribute-to-repopsi/>).

All deposits are subject to enhanced curation, which, among other things, involves converting submitted data to common preservation formats (PDF and ODT files), well-known and widely used in REPOPSI's target user community. The machine-readable XML metadata documents deposited with every digital object (i.e. psychological instrument) on the OSF are in compliance with the latest version of the [DataCite Metadata Schema](#) (Version 4.4).

Preservation plan (R09)

R09. The repository assumes responsibility for long-term preservation and manages this function in a planned and documented way.

Self-Assessed Compliance Level:

0 – In Progress: the repository is in the implementation phase

Response

REPOPSI's data preservation capabilities are largely dependent on the OSF. OSF stores files with long-term and robust preservation in mind. COS established a preservation fund to host a static version of the OSF in the event that COS ceases to function. This fund is sufficient for 50+ years of read access hosting at present costs (<https://help.osf.io/article/546-getting-started-faq-s>). All data

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files on the OSF have a globally unique identifier (GUID). If a data file is deleted or withdrawn, the GUID will always resolve to a page that provides metadata about the removed file (file name, storage provider, if the deletion occurred on OSF or on an add-on service, name/GUID of user who deleted the file, and timestamp of file deletion). For deleted or withdrawn OSF projects and components, a similar page will exist at that GUID noting that the content has been removed (<https://help.osf.io/article/553-project-and-components-faq-s>).

However, REPOPSI currently does not have a preservation fund or a detailed, documented approach to preservation, including plans related to future migrations or a minimum stated preservation period. While the plans are still in the conceptualization phase, REPOPSI implements some practices to ensure long-term data preservation. All data deposits are converted to common preservation formats (PDF and ODT files). The XML documents metadata are deposited with every digital object (i.e. psychological instrument) on the OSF; due to their machine readability, these documents can be used for migration purposes if REPOPSI changes the Repository platform. The regular backup procedure is described in the REPOPSI Maintenance Manual and Workflow (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8195983>).

Quality Assurance (R10)

R10. The repository addresses technical quality and standards compliance, and ensures that sufficient information is available for end users to make quality-related evaluations.

Self-Assessed Compliance Level:

1 – Implemented: the requirement has been fully implemented by the repository

Response

The REPOPSI contribution form (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/how-to-contribute-to-repopsi/>) is designed to ensure sufficient completeness and quality of data and metadata. The form provides detailed guidance for metadata input (e.g. formats) to ensure metadata consistency. The form is separated into several blocks or steps. Each block has a set of mandatory fields (both for the metadata and the psychological instrument itself) and depositors are not allowed to move to the next step unless all required fields are filled in. The same form is used for all contributions; if a need arises to include additional fields, it can be easily modified by the REPOPSI team.

(Meta)data quality is also ensured during enhanced and data-level curation. If a submission fails to meet the required standards, the Repository admin may correct and add the (meta)data or contact the depositor if more information is needed to resolve the issues. Furthermore, the submitted data are converted to common preservation formats (PDF and ODT files). The submitted metadata are

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converted into machine-readable XML documents compliant with the DataCite Metadata Schema. The metadata is enhanced by adding one term (“[Psychological tests](#)”) from the Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH); LCSH is a FAIR-compliant controlled vocabulary, has a machine-readable structure and is documented and resolvable using globally unique and persistent identifiers (<https://fairsharing.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.d31795>).

Workflows (R11)

R11. Digital object management takes place according to defined workflows from deposit to access.

Self-Assessed Compliance Level:

1 – Implemented: the requirement has been fully implemented by the repository

Response

Descriptions of REPOPSI workflows and curation tasks can be found in the “REPOPSI Maintenance Manual and Workflow” document: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8195983>.

This document defines how digital objects are managed from deposit to access; how the workflow is adjusted for different types of (meta)data (e.g. instruments available in full in the Repository vs upon request; original instruments vs instrument translations); how decisions are handled; how changes are managed; and how workflow execution is tracked (with mechanisms to handle exceptions).

The main intended users of this document are the REPOPSI administrator (admin) and REPOPSI associates. The workflow for one digital object can be completed by the admin alone or by the admin and one associate. The document is written in Serbian.

The workflow covers the following tasks: (1) Retrieving user contributions (i.e. deposits obtained via the online contribution form); (2) (Meta)data curation (e.g. putting metadata into tabular inventory files; converting data deposits into PDF and ODT files; enhanced and data-level curations tasks); and (3) Depositing data on the OSF (including populating the OSF component metadata fields and generating XML metadata documents).

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Discovery and Identification (R12)

R12. The repository enables users to discover the digital objects and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation.

Self-Assessed Compliance Level:

1 – Implemented: the requirement has been fully implemented by the repository

Response

OSF assigns a globally unique identifier (GUID) to every metadata record and digital object that it describes (data). Every metadata record has also been assigned Digital Object Identifier (DOI), minted by DataCite (<https://help.osf.io/article/553-project-and-components-faq-s>). This prevents broken links and preserves the accessibility of data stored on the OSF.

REPOPSI supports metadata searching which can be done in several ways (details are available at the [“How to search REPOPSI”](#) page of the website). The most efficient way is using an interactive web app. After entering one or multiple search terms in English, the app shows a table of all of the instrument records matching those terms, including a link to where the accompanying documents are stored on the OSF and how the instruments should be cited. The users are able to download their selection as an XLSX file as well as the complete dataset describing all of the instrument records in the Repository (as a CSV or XLSX file). The app extracts data from the REPOPSI inventory available as a [Google spreadsheet](#). Users can also search REPOPSI directly in the Google spreadsheet or by searching the Inventory [CSV](#) and [XLSX](#) files deposited on the OSF.

Each OSF component in which instruments are stored has a number of specific and accurate “tags” manually added to it. These tags are automatically indexed by search for public content on the OSF (<https://help.osf.io/article/223-tag-your-project>), enhancing data discoverability.

REPOPSI is registered with re3data (<https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100013441>), FAIRsharing (<https://fairsharing.org/4918>), and EOSC Marketplace (<https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/eosc.ubfzf.repopsi>).

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Reuse (R13)

R13. The repository enables reuse of the digital objects over time, ensuring that appropriate information is available to support understanding and use.

Self-Assessed Compliance Level:

1 – Implemented: the requirement has been fully implemented by the repository

Response

The license for the instruments available in full in the Repository (i.e. Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International [CC BY-NC-SA 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/) license) was chosen so that REPOPSI use can be in line with the standards and norms of its target user community (i.e. academic researchers and students). Furthermore, most of the instruments that academic researchers and students develop, adapt or translate can be reused under this license.

The submitted data are converted to common preservation formats (PDF and ODT files), well-known and widely used in REPOPSI's target user community. The submitted metadata are converted into machine-readable XML documents compliant with the DataCite Metadata Schema; the metadata are further enhanced by adding a term from the Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH). Because REPOPSI is used by both local and international researchers, all metadata are in English, while the documentation on the REPOPSI website (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/>) and OSF page (<http://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/5ZB8P>) is provided in both Serbian and English. REPOPSI relies on the OSF because this platform is typically used by psychology researchers (including LIRA researchers) for managing their Open Science projects and collaborations.

The REPOPSI contribution form (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/how-to-contribute-to-repopsi/>) encourages depositors to fully describe the instruments. The field containing the items of the instrument and, if applicable, their presentation order, is mandatory. Depositors are also asked to include the introductory sentences and instructions that respondents receive as well as the response scale on which respondents answer the items (e.g. the number of response categories together with their numerical or verbal labels); this is followed by instructions for instrument administrators, including scoring instructions (e.g. whether an item or scale recoding is necessary, how items are combined to form the total score), and additional notes (e.g. about the translation procedure). They may submit the scoring and recoding code as a file format of their choosing (usually as an SPSS syntax file or R script). These data fields follow a standard recommended by the target research community and support understandability and reuse.

This report was created as part of the project titled "TRUST-ification and FAIR-ification of an open repository for research instruments in psychology: REPOPSI's adoption of RDA outputs", which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017536. The project has received support from the [EOSC Future](#) through the [RDA Open Call mechanism](#), based on evaluations of external, independent experts.

Information Technology & Security

Storage & Integrity (R14)

R14. The repository applies documented processes to ensure data and metadata storage and integrity.

Self-Assessed Compliance Level:

1 – Implemented: the requirement has been fully implemented by the repository

Response

All REPOPSI (meta)data are stored and made openly available on the OSF. Once a digital object is approved and published, only the REPOPSI Team members are able to change the (meta)data. For all (meta)data files deposited on the OSF, a built-in version control maintains a record of all previous copies of a file. Users can access the list of the file's version history, where they are able to copy two types of version IDs (MD5 and SHA-2) and download previous versions of a file (<https://help.osf.io/article/282-file-revisions-and-version-control>). The only exception to this is the REPOPSI inventory available as a public [Google spreadsheet](#); it holds the same metadata set as the Inventory [CSV](#) and [XLSX](#) files deposited on the OSF and only the REPOPSI team members are able to modify it. The spreadsheet is stored in a private folder on [Google Drive](#), which the REPOPSI team use to coordinate their work. The original deposits submitted by users are stored in this Google Drive folder, as well as the curated versions of the data files; the folder, thus, doubles as back-up storage for the Repository contents (as described in the [REPOPSI Maintenance Manual and Workflow](#)).

Technical Infrastructure (R15)

R15. The repository is managed on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and hardware appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community.

Self-Assessed Compliance Level:

1 – Implemented: the requirement has been fully implemented by the repository

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Response

The REPOPSI website (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/>) is hosted by RCUB, which is [an organizational unit of the University of Belgrade](#); in line with their mission and the role of a publicly funded institution, RCUB seeks to provide reliable and secure services.

The psychological instruments available in full in REPOPSI are stored on the OSF (<http://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/5ZB8P>), a free and open-source web application. The OSF is the flagship product of the Center for Open Science (COS; <https://www.cos.io/>), a non-profit organization with the mission of increasing the openness, integrity, and reproducibility of scientific research. OSF stores files with long-term and robust preservation in mind. COS established a preservation fund to host a static version of the OSF in the event that COS ceases to function. This fund is sufficient for 50+ years of read access hosting at present costs (<https://help.osf.io/article/546-getting-started-faq-s>). All public OSF content can be accessed via OSF's open API (documentation is available at <https://developer.osf.io/>).

The interactive web app for searching REPOPSI can be accessed from the "[How to search REPOPSI](#)" page on the REPOPSI website, but is hosted by [shinyapps.io](https://repopsi.shinyapps.io/repopsi/) (<https://repopsi.shinyapps.io/repopsi/>), an online, self-service platform for hosting Shiny apps in the cloud. The service runs in the cloud on shared servers that are operated by [RStudio](https://docs.posit.co/shinyapps.io/) (<https://docs.posit.co/shinyapps.io/>). For the most part, the app was built using the [Shiny package](#) in the [R programming language](#). The app is open-source. The code is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7934950> and new versions of the app will be managed on Zenodo as well.

The online REPOPSI contribution form can be accessed from the "[How to contribute to REPOPSI](#)" page on the REPOPSI website, but is also directly accessible at <https://www.soscisurvey.de/repopsi/>. The form was built using the SoSci Survey (<https://www.soscisurvey.de/>), a software package to create online questionnaires. SoSci Survey is running on a survey server, i.e. [SoSciSurvey.de](https://www.soscisurvey.de), and is handled through one's internet browser (<https://www.soscisurvey.de/help/doku.php/en:start>). Because the REPOPSI contribution form is created by a non-profit organization and for a non-commercial, academic project, [SoSciSurvey.de](https://www.soscisurvey.de) (cloud service) is used free of charge and ad-free.

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Security (R16)

R16. The repository protects the facility and its data, metadata, products, services, and users.

Self-Assessed Compliance Level:

1 – Implemented: the requirement has been fully implemented by the repository

Response

The REPOPSI website (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/>) is hosted by RCUB, which is [an organizational unit of the University of Belgrade](#); in line with their mission and the role of a publicly funded institution, RCUB seeks to provide reliable and secure services.

The psychological instruments available in full in REPOPSI are stored on the OSF (<http://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/5ZB8P>), a free and open-source web application. The OSF is the flagship product of the Center for Open Science (COS; <https://www.cos.io/>). OSF declares that the protection of the stored research data and users' personal information is their top priority (<https://help.osf.io/article/391-security-and-privacy>). More information on OSF security and privacy is available in their help guides at [Security and Privacy - OSF Support](#). COS focuses significant attention on data security, has an established culture of openness, trust, and integrity, and is committed to protecting the OSF's data (<https://help.osf.io/article/228-cos-data-breach-response-plan>). Once a digital object is approved and published, only the REPOPSI team members are able to change the (meta)data stored on the OSF. REPOPSI team members have an account on the OSF and are assigned as "Contributors" to the OSF project and components; only the REPOPSI admin has "Administrator" permissions and they assign either "Read" or "Read + Write" permissions to other contributors (depending on their current roles) (<https://help.osf.io/article/246-understand-contributor-permissions>). All REPOPSI users are "Passive Users" (i.e. persons who may use OSF solely as an information resource without any ability to change or modify any Project content) (<https://www.repopsi.f.bg.ac.rs/en/terms-of-use/>).

The interactive web app for searching REPOPSI is hosted by [shinyapps.io](https://www.shinyapps.io), which is said to be secure-by-design. Each Shiny application runs in its own protected environment and access is always SSL encrypted (<https://www.shinyapps.io/>).

The online REPOPSI contribution form was built using the SoSci Survey software and is running on a [SoSciSurvey.de](https://www.soscisurvey.de) server. SoSci Survey guarantees a high level of data protection – it employs technical measures that protect against unauthorized access and technical failures. More information on this is available at <https://www.soscisurvey.de/en/privacy>. The REPOPSI form itself (<https://www.soscisurvey.de/repopsi/>) includes a security captcha test at the beginning to prevent spam responses.

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